

The Gendered Nature of Tech Entrepreneurship: Understanding the Gender-Divide in Tech Entrepreneurship

Dag Balkmar, Anne-Charlott Callerstig, Gry Agnete Alsos, Tina Bedenik, Marit Breivik-Meyer, Sibylle Heilbrunn, Marta Lindvert, Elisabet Ljunggren, Maura McAdam, and Caren Weinberg

Tool 2

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Levelling the field: A three-part toolbox

This publication is part of a three-part toolbox:

1. *Levelling the field: A Guide to an Inclusive Entrepreneurship Ecosystem* provides a basic understanding of *how to promote* inclusive entrepreneurship from an ecosystem perspective.
2. *The Gendered Nature of Tech Entrepreneurship: Understanding the Gender-divide in Tech Entrepreneurship* is about “the what and whys” related to gender and entrepreneurship, with a particular focus on technical entrepreneurship.
3. *My Better Entrepreneurial Ecosystem: A Workshop on How to Promote an Inclusive Entrepreneurship Ecosystem* provides a format to enhance knowledge, ability and collaboration in an ecosystem focusing on *norm-reflexive ability for change* among actors in the ecosystem.

These three tools are meant as complementary components to inspire change. With the guidebook providing a basic understanding of *how to promote* inclusive entrepreneurship, the report provides deeper *insights into different aspects of gender and inclusion*, and the workshop provides a *format and methods* to enhance knowledge, ability, and collaboration in the ecosystem.

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Introduction

The following publication provides insights - some basic facts and findings - on the complex ways that tech entrepreneurship is gendered. Tech entrepreneurship is typically male dominated. Often the archetypal tech entrepreneur is presented as white American men, names such as Steve Jobs, Jeff Bezos, Elon Musk and Mark Zuckerberg spring to mind. These men are often portrayed as the super-heroes of our time, embodied in heroic narratives such as those associated with masculine risk taking, big money, grandiose tech projects – from the electrification of the car fleet to the colonization of Mars. The fact that they are all men is often taken for granted and naturalized. Even though there are many successful female tech entrepreneurs out there¹, they are rarely elevated in the same way as their popular male tech entrepreneurs counterparts.

Entrepreneurial ecosystems are not neutral spaces. While the success of the venture ideally should be based on the effort, energy, and creativity of the entrepreneur, elements such as race, gender or class also matter.² Although women are influenced by and, in turn, influence ecosystems, empirical evidence explaining how and when variation by gender might apply differentially is absent from most discussions of entrepreneurship ecosystems.³ This is of significance as research⁴ has demonstrated that women are underrepresented in successful entrepreneurial ecosystems, and that a persistent gender bias continues to exist in entrepreneurship.

By providing a gender lens on entrepreneurship, we hope to contribute to insights on how to remedy gendered challenges that can pose a problem not only for an individual but for the whole entrepreneurial ecosystem. We hope that this publication will inspire and create a better understanding into the how and the why, to help you make your entrepreneurial ecosystem more inclusive for all entrepreneurs – regardless of their gender.

The present report is stemming from the GENRE-project; *Overcoming the Entrepreneurship Ecosystem Gender Divide: A Cross-Cultural Perspective* (Heilbrunn et al., 2020, Lindvert et al., 2022, McAdam et al., 2022). GENRE focuses on the cultural embeddedness and interactions of gender, technology, entrepreneurship and innovation

¹ Barnett, 2021

² Broadbridge & Simpson, 2011

³ Brush et al., 2019

⁴ McAdam, 2022

ecosystems by providing a comparison between the four participating countries: Ireland, Sweden, Norway and Israel. In the GENRE project, we have conducted interviews with female and male technology entrepreneurs, with incubator managers and financiers, in Ireland, Sweden, Norway, and Israel. In doing so, we advance knowledge on how contextual factors are constitutive of the strategies which women technology entrepreneurs adopt to develop, grow and enhance their businesses.

Who can become tech entrepreneur?

The gendered nature of tech entrepreneurship

Since early on, feminist writings on gender and technology have been concerned with women's exclusion from technical skills and careers – a perspective that evolved into an analysis of the reproduction of the masculine character of technology itself, of fighting technological determinism and the exclusion of women.⁴⁴ Studies of technology and masculinity has shown the importance of considering how passion, commitment, and love of technology are important elements in how masculinity is formed. Similar traits are also associated with entrepreneurship, including stereotypical notions of entrepreneurship as about being aggressive, competitive, and risk-taking.⁵

Hence, on the one hand, tech entrepreneurship and the figure of the male tech entrepreneur needs to be situated in its historical deep-rooted connection between technology and masculinity.⁶ On the other, men and

⁵ Marlow & Swail, 2014

⁶ Mellström et al. forthcoming

masculinities are simultaneously dynamic and under change. In fact, the GENRE results show that the masculine norms dominating within technology entrepreneurship environments, are by no means representing a masculinity that is inclusive for all men. On the contrary, it is a narrow form of masculinity, where many men are excluded, sometimes questioned if not being ‘masculine’ enough.

The impacts of gender in entrepreneurship show that the prevailing male norm has implications for all the “others” in entrepreneurship: women, ethnic, national and religious minorities, including sexual minorities. The entrepreneurship of those not part of the norm becomes less visible, with implications for founding, funding and growth.

The results of the GENRE project indicate that norms, stereotypes and gendered understandings of technology and entrepreneurship remain challenges in overcoming the gender divide in technology entrepreneurial ecosystems. We refer to a technology entrepreneurial ecosystem as one in which entrepreneurs build their businesses and as the combination of factors for technological innovation that function together in symbiotic relationships. More specifically, the research indicates four main challenges:

1. Navigating technology entrepreneurship ecosystems requires women to enact credible identities to address the tensions arising due to stereotypical notion of the tech entrepreneur.
2. Gendered understandings of technology and entrepreneurship influences investor behaviour and influences the perceived legitimacy of male and female technology entrepreneurs.
3. Gender inequality in technology entrepreneurial ecosystems may be implicit, or even unintentional, a “grey zone”, an experience that is difficult to locate and identify.
4. Women founders often partake in individualized risk assessment to determine the impact of entrepreneurial decisions on their family responsibilities.

In the following, building on these results, we further discuss these challenges with a particular focus on gender and based on the findings from our study.

Women entrepreneurs fitting in?

I have to put a lot of energy into either creating the environment that I want to have, and then I feel it's different compared to a lot of my male colleagues, or I have to put a lot of energy into handling the situation that they are in – an environment that I don't really fit in. So, either/or, I'm putting a lot of energy into somehow adapting to the situation because I'm a woman...I don't see that my male colleagues need to do or even bother to. (Lotten, female tech entrepreneur in Sweden)

In this quote Lotten, a Swedish tech entrepreneur, talks about her incubator experience as a woman. Notably, the quote reflects how a male culture, which envelops the incubator, produces support for identities and characters of the male tenants as the norm, while female tenants, as an underrepresented minority in incubators, must adapt to the prevailing context. Women are underrepresented in successful entrepreneurial ecosystems and a persistent gender bias continues to exist in entrepreneurship discourse and practice. Part of the problem is the implicit assumption that “all entrepreneurs have equal access to resources, participation, and support, as well as an equal chance of a successful outcome (e.g., venture start-up).”⁷ As Lotten explains, she must put a lot of energy into *fitting in* as a female tech entrepreneur, and by doing so she addresses the tensions arising from the stereotypical notion of the tech entrepreneur as typically male.

By listening to women founders' experiences of business incubation we can better understand women's unique experiences and the ways in which gender is performed.⁸ Thus, contextual factors are important to consider, as these are likely to influence women founders' experiences. Interestingly, gender tends to “stick” to women in a very specific way, with gender often used as a proxy for femininity.⁹ Gender refers to socially constructed roles, expectations, and patterns that society devised for each sex, with distinctions made between masculine and feminine characteristics.¹⁰ Gender is a social and cultural practice, enacted and accomplished through

⁷ Brush, et al., 2019, 394

⁸ Sprague, 2016

⁹ Kelan 2009, 166; Ashcraft, 2011

¹⁰ Acker, 1992

doing¹¹ and brought into being through performativity.¹² Importantly, gender is also changeable and dynamic, and context dependent. Consequently, the ways that women and men ‘do’ entrepreneurship is complex, changeable, and shifting across contexts such as different locations, business areas and local circumstances.

Women also take up typically ‘masculine’ practices, for example through the adoption of particular gestures and dress. This adoption is sometimes referred to the *honorary man persona*¹³ and refers to a coping strategy often adopted by women within the technology field to fit in with the masculinity of the sector.¹⁴ Women complying to normative dress codes or manners to generate a credible situated image is not only applicable to women. To comply – or not comply with – stereotypical notions of gender and gendered behaviour are something we all have to relate to. However, our study shows that female founders had developed strategies to blend in with the prevailing incubator culture in an attempt to overcome “otherness”. Dress codes are often used by women to ‘adjust’ to male dominated cultures, and by doing so, concealing overt femininity enabling women to blend with the (masculine) context.¹⁵ Our findings showed how the female founders tried to accommodate entrepreneurial masculinity by *fitting in*.¹⁶ One of our conclusions is that in order to make the ecosystem more inclusive, and better in accommodating women, key in achieving inclusiveness is to challenge the male norm.

Or challenging the male norm?

The cultural norms related to what constitutes technology entrepreneurship and who engages in entrepreneurship is ingrained in all four participating ecosystems to varying degrees. Consequently, a reinforcing set of assumptions genders the image of the typical technology entrepreneur – he is male.

¹¹ West & Zimmerman, 1987

¹² Gherardi, 1995

¹³ Ogbor, 2000

¹⁴ Trauth, 2002

¹⁵ Bjorkman et al., 1997

¹⁶ Trauth, 2002; Martin et al., 2015

In order for women and other minority groups to benefit more from incubation, challenging of tacit presumptions and dismantling of an entrenched masculinized culture is needed.¹⁷ Evidence from our study indicated that such norms could be challenged through the expansion of *current conceptualisations* of the stereotypical technology entrepreneur, a *change in the language and narratives* around technology entrepreneurship, and the *involvement of women* in the development and design of incubators and associated support structures.

The implications of not fitting in with the idealised image of the male technology entrepreneur, differ across contexts, in our study several differences were detected between the countries. For example, some female founders in Israel experience inappropriate comments about their physical appearance and femaleness, whilst in Ireland, previous experiences of gender discrimination and sexism in the workplace negatively influenced women's self-confidence and led to the emergence of imposter syndrome. In the Swedish context, the women referred to not being taken seriously, experiencing issues with mansplaining and more generally being treated in a patronising manner. Even though there were some accounts of gender discrimination and sexism also in Sweden, it was assumed that strong national gender equality policies had eliminated such behaviours. This often creates a '*gendered dilemma*'.¹⁸ This dilemma arises from the conflict between simultaneous denial and yet experiencing inequalities. Non-normative entrepreneurs may interpret discriminatory behaviours as an odd individual occurrence or as general accepted organizational rules-of-the game. In short, women negotiate tensions arising from being women and not being 'men'.¹⁹ This was evident in our study where incubator tenants experienced how expectations were perceived to be higher for women than for men. In particular, the women felt they needed to be better qualified and to work harder than their male counterparts to stand out.

From our interviews with female founders, it is very clear that they recognize the presence of gender-related challenges in the overall entrepreneurial ecosystem in their respective countries.

¹⁷ Godwin, Stevens, & Brenner, 2006

¹⁸ Kelan, 2010

¹⁹ Butler, 2004

However, they often tend to attribute the challenges to ‘other women’ rather than to themselves. When specific examples were asked for, we often got stories about their female friends, or the experiences of other women they knew of. The overall impression from the data is that the female founders emphasize that *they take control* and seek to be in charge of their own funding process. It is important for them to be portrayed as *strong, independent actors* and not as victims. (Lindvert et al., 2022)

Women founders negotiating risk

The findings from our study show how women founders partake in individualized *risk assessment* to determine the impact of their decisions to become an entrepreneur on their family responsibilities. The ways women founders thought about risks was related also to their age and life stage. Although entrepreneurship more generally was posited as providing entrepreneurs with increased freedom, autonomy, and flexibility, some of the founders, especially women, suggested that entrepreneurship can also generate a lack of security. This can be understood at the background of women’s higher share of unpaid work – applicable to all four studied countries - and which is the case in most countries around the world. In the Nordic welfare states featured in the study – Sweden and Norway – the general family friendly working life has not expanded into the realm of entrepreneurship. The disparity between relative benefits between employed and self-employed was evident.

The findings from our study show how women sometimes act in ways that are more risk-averse than their male counterparts due to unequal division of domestic care labour in their families. However, we also found that risk typically tends to be associated with men and masculinities, thus, women may be deemed risk averse against this standard.²⁰ Therefore, a *more nuanced understanding of risk taking is required* in relation to the lived experiences of female technology entrepreneurs at the different stages of their life cycle. (McAdam et al., 2022)

²⁰ Marlow & Swail, 2014

Gendered investor behavior

I'm a little unsure, maybe. I think that a woman may have to work a little extra to convince, that there has been a slightly oppressed minority of women lately. I guess the female entrepreneurs have been in a tougher battle to get investments, and to convince investors. It can give strength again later by training so well and working on it, so I think it can provide an even better starting point for the next investment round or future situations.' (Alf, a Norwegian angel investor)

Alf, one of the young Norwegian angels reflects on the need for gender awareness among investors and how gender impacts the quest for investments. What Alf says is well in line with previous research, that has shown that women entrepreneurs obtain less capital compared to men²¹, particularly when looking at venture capital.²² Explanations to the gender gap in financing have been sought on both the demand and supply side of capital. For example, it has been argued that the disparity depends on differences in social or human capital, risk preferences or strategic choices.²³ However, there is still no satisfactory explanation to the prevailing gender gap in financing²⁴ and it is especially puzzling that access to capital still differs between men and women entrepreneurs in countries, otherwise known to be gender equal, such as in the Nordic countries in our study.²⁵

We're indifferent to gender. I mean, we meet a person and we are looking objectively at the technology, how they approach the market, we're looking at objective things rather than gender. I'm also involved in food-tech, so in general what I'm interested in is to do good. We are also in the healthcare domain... we're looking at impact, how we could impact this planet and how we could do good. This is important to us... We are looking for an entrepreneur with a soul. It doesn't matter if it's a woman or a man, they need to have a sense of purpose. That they are not only in it for the money. (Dana, an investor from Israel)

²¹ Alsos et al., 2006

²² Brush et al., 2018

²³ Carter et al., 2003

²⁴ Leitch et al., 2018

²⁵ Husu & Callerstig, 2018

In this quote, Dana, an Israeli investor, reflects on the investment strategy from a gender perspective. The will to do good is stressed rather than what gender an entrepreneur might have - someone with “a soul” rather than being in it for the money. While most Israeli investors stated that they would be happy to invest more in female-led start-ups, only a few of them were actively trying to search out female entrepreneurs in their field (through women-in-tech networks), and none of them had a declared gender-equality agenda underpinning their investments.

It is a common theme in our study that the investors stress that they look at investments ‘objectively’. Against this background we stress the capability to ‘see gender’ as important. And although the majority of interviewed investors in this research recognise the presence of gender-related challenges in their entrepreneurial ecosystem, very few reflected on their own role in this system. Rather, they attributed problems to:

- *Other investors.* A common argument was that one really treats women and men the same, but that other investors fail to do so.
- *The women.* In line with previous research, we found that investors often place the problem on the demand side, arguing that women are lacking ambitions, lacking network or lacking resources. It was also commonly argued that women have different focus, are risk averse, have more domestic responsibilities or prioritize family life, and therefore have less time to focus on the start-up.
- *Pipeline issues.* Lastly, almost all investors argued that there are pipeline issues, with too few women in STEM-sectors, too few women entrepreneurs, too few women tech entrepreneurs, and consequently it is difficult to find good investment cases.

Research in Sweden has shown that investors make a difference in how they talk about women and men even though the entrepreneurs’ background and applications are very similar. Investors do this even when they believe they are gender neutral in their discussions. Studies show that women who run companies are considered prudent - they are assumed not to take large loans or make large investments, they are expected to only need small funds and be active in areas with less growth potential. On the contrary, men who run companies are considered to dare to invest, need

large funds and be active in areas that are financially viable and to have growth potential.²⁶

Women entrepreneurs experience gender-related funding challenges in all four countries. Challenges are less evident in relation to soft funding (at a very early stage, when public funding or grants are sought for) but increasingly evident when reaching for equity funding. From our research, it is clear how gendered understandings of technology and entrepreneurship influences investor behaviour and influences the perceived legitimacy of male and female technology entrepreneurs. Our findings show several examples of gender-related funding challenges. Some of the most frequently expressed are:

- *Informal networks.* Women express that they have less access to informal networks that give access to investors or information about different opportunities.
- *Less legitimacy.* Women experience that investors attribute them with less legitimacy, and question their ability to grow their start-ups.
- *Asked different questions.* Women are asked different questions by investors, e.g., asked about the worst-case scenario rather than about potential upside.
- *Business sector.* Gender-related funding challenges are intertwined with the business sector; women in female dominated and male dominated sectors experience somewhat different challenges.

A strong theme in our findings is that the challenges met often are *subtle and hidden*, it is something that happens in the “grey zones” in relation to investors. As such, it is difficult to pinpoint, recognize and account for.

Our findings show how women and men are assessed differently by investors, even when they may have the same potential and when gender neutrality is stressed as being important to apply in the assessment process. However, it is difficult to see a decisive pattern in exactly *how* gender operates and *what effect* it causes, which is in line with other research findings. From earlier research we know that assessments and negotiations in related areas (such as in applications for research funding) often result in

²⁶ Malmström et al., 2017a and 2017b; Malmström & Johansson 2015

gender differences and especially in relation to financial outcomes. These studies have shown that gender is not a stable factor in predicting effects in assessment and negotiation situations. Rather, it serves as a trigger for gendered behaviours. This is especially in situations where assessment criteria is imprecise and implicitly associated with strong gendered norms (such as tech entrepreneurship) and where decisions may to some degree rely on “gut-feeling”.²⁷ To minimise the risk of gender bias we suggest a combination of gender training, formalisation of assessment criteria and decision making processes.

Strategies used by women entrepreneurs

When analysing the rich data from our study, we found that women entrepreneurs use several different strategies to overcome gender-related challenges. These strategies refer to experiences of not fitting in tech entrepreneurial settings, they offer ways to overcome the gender related funding challenges encountered and for coping with family responsibilities. Four main strategies were used sometimes in parallel, and applied differently depending on situation and context. These were:

- *Ignoring.* First, women can choose to ignore the challenges, and act as if they do not exist. This may be a strategy to choose to be passive, to not waste energy on what is difficult to change, but to try to focus on what is possible to improve (the start-up).
- *Fighting.* A second strategy is to fight gender-related challenges, by actively making them visible. This is an active approach, where gender is brought to the agenda and where the founder actively works for change, maybe by organizing other women or by requiring change by other actors within the ecosystem.
- *Navigating.* A third strategy is to navigate the challenges. Similar to the previous strategy, this is an active way of acknowledging the challenges, but focusing on internal actions rather than external factors. For example, women can choose to team up with a man when pitching for investors, to ‘use the woman card’, or to make sure to obtain female support by, for example, searching for female investors.

²⁷ see Riley & McGinn, 2002

- *Accepting*. Lastly, we found that a strategy to deal with challenges can be acceptance. It is a passive strategy, but as opposed to simply ignoring the challenges, acceptance means that existing challenges are recognized. The reasoning can be that ‘change will come with next generations’ or that one simply reduces the ambitions for the start-up.

Conclusions

Research has convincingly demonstrated that women are underrepresented in successful entrepreneurial ecosystems, and that a persistent gender bias continues to exist in entrepreneurship, affecting who gets supported in, and by, the system.²⁸ By providing a nuanced understanding of how gender is a decisive factor, i.e., how women and men are influenced by and, in turn, influence entrepreneurial ecosystems differently, the GENRE project has contributed to insights on how to remedy gendered problems and make your entrepreneurial ecosystem more inclusive.

In GENRE, we have found that women must enact credible identities to address the tensions arising from the stereotypical notion of the tech entrepreneur as male. We have learned that gendered understandings of technology and entrepreneurship influences investor behaviour and influences the perceived legitimacy of male and female technology entrepreneurs. The assessments are vague and gender inequality is often implicit, difficult to locate and identify. Despite seemingly gender-neutral assessment criteria these are used in different ways in the assessment of women and men to the advantage of men.

While there are obvious similarities across the four studied countries, in terms of size, population and economies, there are also obvious differences to consider across the studied ecosystems. Sweden and Norway are countries with long traditions of working with gender equality issues from a public policy side. Despite policies and welfare systems in place to facilitate equal participation on the job market for both men and women, the labour markets in each country are strongly gender segregated. Israel and Ireland stand out with strong values associated with family and religious values influencing society – including strong family norms. Despite the differences,

²⁸ McAdam et al., 2019

the associations between men, masculinity and tech entrepreneurship remains a strong theme across all four ecosystems.

One of the key challenges identified by the GENRE project is how gender inequality in technology entrepreneurial ecosystems can be implicit, even unintentional, described as a “grey zone.” In short, it is an experience that is difficult to locate and identify. Hence, there is a need to make explicit, identify and address the gendered problems of an entrepreneurial ecosystem. A way forward is to consider the following four sets of conditions for a more inclusive entrepreneurial ecosystem: density, fluidity, connectivity, and diversity of opportunity.²⁹ In all four domains, *women’s entrepreneurial activity is underrepresented*.³⁰

- In terms of *density*, the relative share of women in and entering into entrepreneurship is lower than for men.³¹
- In terms of *fluidity*, women are leaving employment in STEM-based industries, due to a hostile environment, gender bias and glass wall/ceiling effects, reducing their potential entrepreneurial contribution.³²
- In terms of *connectivity*, where networks do exist, they are not gender inclusive and women do not participate.³³
- Finally, in terms of *diversity of opportunity*, women are significantly under-represented in what is still a highly masculinized domain.³⁴

Women are included in the yearly “Missing Entrepreneurs” reports published by the European Commission and the OECD since 2014. These reports examine how targeted public policies can help to overcome obstacles to start-ups and self-employment and assume that the underrepresentation is due to factors such as institutional barriers, discrimination related difficulties to access resources, skill gaps etc. As shown in the present data, women obviously *do* manage to navigate in

²⁹ Stangler & Bell-Masterson, 2015

³⁰ McAdam et al. 2019, p. 459

³¹ Motoyama et al., 2014

³² Bilimoria et al., 2014

³³ Watkins, 2015

³⁴ Ahl, 2006

masculine technology environments, and they *do* express strength and self-confidence, and use all kinds of strategies in their everyday incubator interactions and in the process of raising capital. There seems to be a need for a different set of questions: Rather than asking, ‘why so few women’, we might as well ask, ‘how come tech entrepreneurship is so attractive to men?’ This would suggest a move from a ‘fix the women’ approach, to addressing how the system is benefitting (some forms of) men and masculinities. By critically engaging with the masculine norms prevailing in tech entrepreneurship we can reframe taken for granted and stereotypical assumptions about tech entrepreneurship.

REFERENCES

- Acker, J., (1992). From sex roles to gendered institutions. *Contemporary sociology*, 21(5), 565-569.
- Ashcraft, K.L., (2011). Knowing work through the communication of difference: A Revised Agenda for Difference Studies. *Reframing difference in organizational communication studies: Research, pedagogy, practice*, Sage Publications, 3-29.
- Ahl, H. (2006). 'Why Research on Women Entrepreneurs Needs New Directions', *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*, 30(5), 596–621.
- Alsos, G. A., Isaksen, E. J., & Ljunggren, E. (2006). New venture financing and subsequent business growth in men- and women-led businesses. *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*, 30(5), 667-686.
- Barnet, J., (2021). Top 10 Women in Tech, Tech Funnels, [\(99+\) Top 10 Women In Tech 2021 | LinkedIn](#), accessed Oct 10, 2022
- Bilimoria, D., Lord, L. & Marinelli, M., (2014). An introduction to women in STEM careers: international perspectives on increasing workforce participation, advancement and leadership. In D. B. KeyBank, L. Lord, M. Bickley (Eds.) *Women in STEM Careers*, Edward Elgar Publishing.
- Bjorkman, C., Christoff, I., Palm, F. & Vallin, A. (1997). *Women in Computing*. Exeter, Intellectual Books.
- Broadbridge, A. & Simpson, R., (2011). 25 years on: reflecting on the past and looking to the future in gender and management research. *British Journal of Management*, 22(3), 470-483.
- Brush, C. G., Greene, P., Balachandra, L., & Davis, A. (2018). The gender gap in venture capital-progress, problems, and perspectives. *Venture Capital*, 20(2), 115-136.
- Brush, C., Edelman, L.F., Manolova, T. & Welter, F. (2019). A Gendered Look at Entrepreneurship Ecosystems', *Small Business Economics*, 53, 393–408.
- Butler, J., (2004). *Undoing gender*. New York, Routledge.
- Carter, N., Brush, C., Greene, P., Gatewood, E., & Hart, M. (2003). Women entrepreneurs who break through to equity financing: The influence of human, social and financial capital. *Venture Capital*, 5(1), 1-28.
- Gherardi, S. (1995). *Gender, symbolism and organizational cultures*. London, Sage.

Godwin, L., Stevens, C. & Brenner, N. (2006). Forced to play by the rules? Theorizing how mixed sex teams benefit women in male dominated contexts. *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*, 30(5), 623-642.

Heilbrunn, S., Alsos, G.A., Arntzen-Nordqvist, M., Balkmar, D., Callerstig, A.C., Delaney, D., Gulli Lindvert, M., Ljunggren, E. C., McAdam, M., Mellström, U. and Weinberg, C. (2020). *Cross-cultural Variations in Technological Ecosystems, a Gender Perspective*. Kinneret College on the Sea of Galilee, Israel. ISBN 978-965-599-388-2

Husu, L. & Callerstig, A. (2018). Riksbankens Jubileumsfonds beredningsprocesser ur ett jämställdhetsperspektiv. Stockholm: Riksbankens Jubileumsfond (RJ rapporterar 2018:1).

Kelan, E. (2009). *Performing gender at work*. Basingstoke, Palgrave Macmillan.

Kelan, E.K., (2010). Gender logic and (un) doing gender at work. *Gender, Work & Organization*, 17(2), 174-194.

Leitch, C., Welter, F., & Henry, C. (2018). Women entrepreneurs' financing revisited: taking stock and looking forward. *Venture Capital*, 20(2), 103-114.

Lindvert, M., Breivik-Meyer, M., Alsos, G.A., Balkmar, D., Bedenik, T., Callerstig, A.C., Delaney, D., Heilbrunn, S., Ljunggren, E.C., McAdam, M., and Weinberg, C. (2022). *A Cross-cultural Examination of Investor Behaviour – the influence of gendered understandings*, Nord University, Norway.

Martin, L., Wright, L., Beaven, Z. & Matlay, H. (2015). An unusual job for a woman? Female entrepreneurs in scientific, engineering and technology sectors. *International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behavior & Research*, 21(4), 539–556.

Marlow, S., & Swail, J. (2014). Gender, risk and finance: why can't a woman be more like a man? *Entrepreneurship & Regional Development*, 26(1-2), 80-96.

McAdam, M., Harrison, R.T. & Leitch, C.M. (2019). Stories from the field: Women's networking as gender capital in entrepreneurial ecosystems. *Small Business Economics*, 53(2), 459-474.

McAdam, M., Delaney, D., Bedenik, T., Heilbrunn, S., Callerstig, A-C., Balkmar, D., Lindvert, M., Alsos, G. A., Ljunggren, E. C., Breivik-Meyer, M., and Weinberg, C. (2022). *Cross-cultural variations in technology incubation provision: An examination of representation and gender dynamics*. Ireland: Dublin City University (DCU).

Malmström, M., & Johansson, J. (2015). *Under ytan: Hur går snacket och vem får pengarna II?*, Stockholm, Tillväxtverket.

Malmström, M., Johansson, J., & Wincent, J. (2017a). We Recorded VCs' Conversations and Analyzed How Differently They Talk About Female Entrepreneurs. *Harvard Business Review* (May 2017).

Malmström, M., Johansson, J., & Wincent, J. (2017b). Gender Stereotypes and Venture Support Decisions: How Governmental Venture Capitalists Socially Construct Entrepreneurs' Potential. *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*, 41(5), 833-860.

Mellström, U., Balkmar, D. & Callerstig, A-C. (forthcoming). Tracing the superheroes of our time: Contemporary and emergent masculinities in tech entrepreneurship. In K. Aavik, D. Collinson, J. Hearn, & A. Thym, *Routledge Handbook of Men, Masculinities and Organizations: Theories, Practices and Futures of Organizing*. London/New York, Routledge.

Motoyama, Y., Konczal, J., Bell-Masterson, J., & Morelix, A. (2014). Think Locally, Act Locally: Building a Robust Entrepreneurial Ecosystem. Kansas City, Kauffman Foundation.

Ogbor, J. (2000). Mythicizing and Reification in Entrepreneurial Discourse: Ideology-critique of entrepreneurship studies. *Journal of Management Studies* 37(5), 605-635.

Riley, H., & McGinn K.L. (2002). When Does Gender Matter in Negotiation? John F. Kennedy School of Government, Harvard University Faculty Research Working Papers Series RWP02-036, September 2002.

Sprague, J. (2016). *Feminist methodologies for critical researchers: Bridging differences*. Rowman & Littlefield.

Stangler, D., & Bell-Masterson, J. (2015). Measuring an Entrepreneurial Ecosystem. Kauffman Foundation Research Series on City, Metro and Regional Entrepreneurship', Kansas City, Kauffman Foundation.

Trauth, E.M. (2002). Odd girl out: an individual differences perspective on women in the IT profession. *Information Technology & People*, 15(2), 98-118.

Watkins, K. K. (2015). Examining the connections within the start-up ecosystem, paper to DIANA International Research Conference, Babson College, MA, 8–9 June.

West, C., & Zimmerman, D.H. (1987). Doing gender. *Gender & society*, 1(2), 125-151.

GENRE is a three-year research project that aims to investigate and cross-culturally compare the lived experiences of female technology entrepreneurs in incubation and investing ecosystems in four different countries. The findings generated inform policy development aimed at inclusivity and sustainability, thus benefiting both women and men. It is a transnational research project taking place simultaneously in Ireland (Dublin City University), Norway (Nord University), Sweden (Karlstad and Örebro University) and Israel (Kinneret College). The project is coordinated by DCU Business School (Dublin) and led by Prof Maura McAdam. GENRE is co-funded under the GENDER-NET Plus Joint Call Grant Number GNP-122.

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